

Augmenting a Smartphone Camera with a Telephoto Lens for Enhanced LED-to-Camera Communication

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ABSTRACT—In LED-to-Smartphone Camera communication, the camera detects the status of the light source (ON or OFF) in each frame to receive information. If the light source is modulated faster than a single frame duration, there are multiple white & dark stripes corresponding to the transmitted information bits. Further, the receiver’s region of interest in LED-to-Smartphone Camera communication is limited by the size of the light source in the frame in terms of the number of pixels. As the distance between the LED and the camera increases, the light source does not cover the whole frame, resulting in a significant amount of data loss. Therefore, LED-to-Smartphone Camera communication is limited by distance, making it difficult to transmit data from several meters away. On the other hand, there is a loss of data even at relatively short ranges due to small region of interest, especially for tiny light sources. In this work, we enhance the smartphone camera with a telephoto lens that provides optical zoom on the light source and increases the region of interest. The optical zoom from a telephoto lens helps the user focus on the light source and reduces data loss. We compare the data transfer rate with and without a telephoto lens at short distances (15-80 cm). The initial results show that a telephoto lens improves the data transfer rate at short distances and also expands the possible range for LED-to-Smartphone Camera links.

Index Terms—visible light communication, CMOS sensors, optics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless communication highly uses the radio frequency (RF) spectrum to transfer valuable information from device to device. However, the increasing use of wireless devices is putting pressure on the limited RF spectrum [1], leading to a phenomenon known as “spectrum crunch.” New ways to optimize spectrum allocation or use other parts of the electromagnetic spectrum, such as visible light or infrared, are needed to overcome these limitations and provide additional capacity for wireless communication. One example is Visible Light Communication (VLC) [2], which uses the wider visible light spectrum to transmit data. VLC can use various types of transmitters such as light bulbs, screens, and liquid crystal cells, and receivers such as photodiodes, cameras, and solar cells to transfer information.

A key combination for IoT applications is the use of LEDs as transmitters and smartphone cameras as receivers, known as LED-to-Smartphone Camera (L2C) communication, due to the widespread use of both. According to market estimates, there are over 6.2 billion smartphone users worldwide [3] and the

Fig. 1: Two consecutive frames: data loss in L2C communication due to small ROI (red arrows) and inter-frame duration.

compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of the global LED market size is 11.0% from 2023 to 2030 based on a recent report, thanks to its low energy consumption and long lifetime [4]. Smartphone users can interact with light sources both indoors and outdoors, enabling various applications such as human-computer interaction, sensing, and augmented reality [5]–[11]. Examples include home and city automation applications that use small LEDs in appliances, parking meters, or thermostats to communicate their status [5], [6].

In L2C communication, digital information is transmitted mainly through changes in light intensity or color. The smartphone camera records the modulated light source information as a video, which is then separated into frames. Digital information is extracted through image processing techniques from each frame. However, the inter-frame-gap duration defined as the time gap between two consecutive frames affects the achievable data rate, because the camera does not capture information bits during this period (Figure 1). Furthermore, the appearance of the LED image on each frame is critical for decoding the transmitted information [12]. The image sensors on the camera create this appearance corresponding to the incident light. Most smartphones use Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor (CMOS) image sensors, which consist of a 2D array of pixel sensors [13]. Each pixel sensor converts the incident light into a voltage value. In CMOS sensors, each row of pixel sensors sequentially collects the photons

in a line-by-line scanning method called the rolling shutter image acquisition method [14]. This method benefits L2C communication to achieve higher data rates by modulating the light intensity faster than the frame duration which causes multiple stripes of white (LED ON) & dark (LED OFF) to appear on the image based on the modulation frequency. Each stripe corresponds to information bits.

Data Transfer Rate (DTR) Limitations in L2C: In L2C communication, the rolling shutter method allows for higher data rates, and the maximum achievable data rate is possible when the LED image covers the entire frame. However, the appearance of the LED size in the camera frame is determined by the distance between the LED and the camera, affecting the maximum achievable data rate. The loss in data rate is significant even at shorter link distances, especially for very small light sources. Figure 1 shows the captured modulated LED source (physical size of 2.06 cm) at a link distance of 25 cm, covering only 122 pixels out of the 1080 pixels, resulting in a significant loss of information bits due to the lack of vertical resolution. This limits the range of applications as the region of interest (ROI) is small. Therefore, small ROI highlights developing solutions to improve the data rate by increasing the ROI and reducing the effect of the link distance.

Contributions. To overcome the aforementioned *region of interest* limitation, this paper proposes an optical-zoom-based technique to improve the data rate of LED-to-smartphone-based communication systems by using a telephoto lens. Differently from a digital zoom, which makes objects appear closer without affecting the data rate, the use of an optical zoom by way of a telephoto lens helps to minimize the loss in data rate at shorter link distances and increases the communication range by having a larger focal length. Our study suggests that the use of a telephoto lens can improve the data rate of L2C communication links.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II explains the L2C communication link and the camera parameters that affect the achievable data rate. Section III, provides a detailed explanation of the proposed solution for the small ROI problem. Section IV includes the experimental evaluation of the telephoto lens. Section V reviews the related work on the use of lenses in L2C communication.

II. LED-TO-SMARTPHONE COMMUNICATION

In this section, the implemented L2C communication link is introduced, and the effect of camera parameters on the achievable data rate is described.

A. System Overview

The block diagram of the implemented L2C link is depicted in Figure 2. The Arduino UNO microcontroller controls the transmission of data sequences, which are sent to the LED driver for modulation via On-Off Keying (OOK). The LED driver adjusts the LED intensity to encode digital information based on whether the LED is on or off. The receiver employs the rolling shutter acquisition method to capture multiple bits in a single frame. A smartphone records a video of the transmission, and image processing is performed on the

Fig. 2: L2C link block diagram.

resulting frames to extract the digital information. Specifically, the image processing extracts the waveform from a frame in terms of pixel values (with a range of 0-255 based on brightness). The steps involved in image processing are to convert each frame first into a grey-scale image. After grey-scaling, a threshold is applied to have two values as a pixel value in the frame (0 or 255 based on the threshold value). The waveform is extracted from the column position corresponding to the center of the light source. To determine this column position, the sum of pixel values from each column is calculated and the column with the maximum value is selected. Finally, digital information is obtained based on the width of each white & dark band in the waveform.

B. Data Transfer Rate

In L2C communication, the Data Transfer Rate (DTR) depends on how many times the status (ON or OFF) of the light source can be detected in a single frame. In the rolling shutter images, there is a series of white & dark bands, where the number of bits in a single frame depends on the size of the light source and the width of the single band (Equation 1). S_v represents the size of the light source in terms of the number of pixels, and W_b represents the width of a single band in terms of the number of pixels. The average number of bits in a single frame, N_s given as [15]

$$N_s = \frac{S_v + W_b - 1}{W_b} \quad (1)$$

The DTR is obtained by multiplying the average number of bits (N_s) with the frame rate of the camera. The number of bits is determined by the number of bands within the light source in a frame. The width of the band depends on the modulation frequency (f) of the light source and the readout time of the camera (t_r) (Equation 2). The readout time is the time required to assign pixel values for one array of pixel sensors based on the collected photons during the exposure time. When the exposure time is very low, the readout time can be interpreted as the scanning duration of one array of pixel sensors in a 2D sensor. Since the readout time is specific for any smartphone camera, the width of the band is mainly determined by the modulation frequency. Furthermore, the width of the band does not change with the distance between the pair. However, the size of the light source changes based on the distance.

(a) ISO: 20

(b) ISO: 100

Fig. 3: Effect of ISO values on the appearance of LED in a single camera frame (link distance = 30cm).

$$W_b = \frac{1}{ft_r} \quad (2)$$

1) Effect of camera parameters on DTR

On the receiver side, some camera parameters of the smartphone, such as the exposure time and ISO value, have a critical impact on the reception. The array of pixel sensors collects light during the exposure time, and a longer exposure time increases the chance of getting brighter pixels. The ISO value defines the sensitivity of the camera to light, and a higher ISO value results in higher sensitivity and an increased chance of getting brighter pixels, but also decreases the contrast between dark and white bands, and increases the chance of getting noise [16]. These camera parameters (ISO and exposure time) can be controlled using smartphone applications such as the Open Camera app for Android or the ProMovie app for iOS.

The number of pixels corresponding to the light source mainly determines the DTR (Equation 1). The light may cover a larger area than the light source's physical diameter in the frame, resulting in a *blooming effect* which depends on the radiation pattern and intensity of the light source as well as the ISO value and exposure time of the smartphone camera. The camera captures a range of light intensities. With the higher the ISO value, the more it captures the less intense parts. Lowering the ISO value filters out these parts and shows the light source at its true size. Figure 3 illustrates this using images taken with an iPhone 7 Plus at the same distance and exposure time, but with different ISO values. As seen in the figure, higher ISO values lead to brighter and larger images of the light source.

2) Effect of LED-Camera orientation on DTR.

The position of the smartphone and the light source affects how much light is captured, and this can cause the light source to appear larger or smaller in the frame, particularly when the

(a) Minimum data rate

(b) Maximum data rate

Fig. 4: DTR dependant on the position of the LED-Camera pair (with the same ISO value and same link distance).

LED and the camera are close together. Figure 4 illustrates this using images taken with a Galaxy A7 smartphone at a distance of 15 cm, with the same exposure time (1/71429 seconds) and ISO value (100), but with different positions of the light source. When the smartphone and light source are directly facing each other, additional bands appear in the frame. In Figure 4a, the size of the light source is small, which results in a low data rate- minimum DTR condition and in Figure 4b, the light intensity is high and the number of bands is greater, resulting in the highest possible data rate- maximum DTR condition.

III. LEVERAGING A TELEPHOTO LENS TO INCREASE THE DATA TRANSFER RATE

In L2C communication, there are two sources of data loss: inter-frame duration and incomplete region of interest. The time gap (inter-frame duration) between consecutive frames leads to a loss of data during this period. Additionally, as the LED light source does not typically fill the entire frame, information can also be lost within a single frame. The challenge of ROI can be overcome in two ways: using the digital zoom feature of the camera and using the proposed method of optical zoom i.e. employing a telephoto lens with the smartphone camera lens. The latter involves using another lens with a larger focal length. In the following section, we will explain how optical zoom performs better than digital zoom alone and helps to improve the achievable data rate.

A. Mobile Zoom

The use of mobile zoom allows the user to capture a subject or object at a closer distance and with greater detail than would be possible with the default camera settings. It is done by increasing the magnification of the lens, which can be done digitally or optically. Digital zoom is achieved by cropping and

(a) Without digital zoom

(b) With digital zoom (x4)

Fig. 5: Digital zoom makes object bigger proportional to zooming factor.

enlarging the image after it is captured, which can result in a loss of image quality. Optical zoom, on the other hand, uses the lens to physically change the focal length, which preserves image quality.

Effect of Digital Zoom on DTR. Intuitively, it may seem that using the phone’s zoom function would help to capture more data by focusing the light source and fitting it into the entire frame, but in reality, the phone’s digital zoom does not significantly increase the data rate. This is because the phone’s zoom only enlarges the focused object in proportion to the zoom factor. The data rate depends on the size and width of the band. When using zoom, the size of the LED and the width of the band are multiplied by the digital zoom factor of the camera, for example, if it’s x4 zoom, the size is multiplied by 4 in terms of the number of pixels. Since the size of the LED and the width of the band increase at the same ratio, the data rate does not change significantly, see equation 1. Figure 5 illustrates the effect of digital zoom on L2C communication using a Galaxy A7 smartphone. The smartphone receives an information sequence of $\{1, 0\}$ at a frequency of 1 kHz from a distance of 25 cm. The readout time of the Galaxy A7 is 22.4 microseconds and the width of a single bit is about 45 pixels. In Figure 5a, there is no digital zoom and the width of five consecutive bands is as follows: 45, 45, 45, 50, and 10 pixels. In Figure 5b, there is a zoom factor of x4. The determined width of five consecutive bands is as follows: 180, 180, 175, 190, and 105 pixels from the same distance. The width of the complete bands (with 45 pixels) is multiplied by the zoom factor. The number of bands does not change in the two cases, therefore the DTR remains nearly the same when digital zoom is used.

B. Telephoto Lens

A telephoto lens performs optical zoom that allows one to zoom in on distant objects. It does this by having a larger focal length than a standard lens, which helps to bring the subject closer and into focus. When smartphone user uses a

(a) Without telephoto lens (50 cm)

(b) With telephoto lens (50 cm)

Fig. 6: Telephoto lens provides bigger ROI for L2C communication.

telephoto lens, they can directly focus on the light source, which reduces the amount of light/data that is lost within the frame. Additionally, a telephoto lens allows for focusing light at relatively far distances. In our case, the LED diameter is 2.06 cm and it would not be possible to take advantage of a rolling shutter after a distance of 1 meter with this diameter. However, with a telephoto lens, it is possible to reach several meters in range. Figure 6 provides an example of comparing a frame appearance with and without a telephoto lens from a distance of 50 cm, where the ROI becomes much larger and the width of the band is the same as without the telephoto lens.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We have carried out an experimental assessment of the impact of a telephoto lens. The transmitter used in the experiments is an MCE4WT LED controlled by an Arduino-UNO. The receiver is a Galaxy A7 smartphone equipped with a Apexel HD x22 telephoto lens, which is mounted on the smartphone via an adapter ring. Two evaluation points are considered in the experiments: a) DTR comparison at the smartphone with and without the telephoto lens at relatively short distances (15-80 cm), b) Determining the achievable range with the telephoto lens.

In the first case, the goal is to examine the amount of additional data that the smartphone can capture with the lens at relatively short distances. The experiments are conducted within a range of 15-80 cm. The starting distance is 15 cm because the telephoto lens has a length of 10.6 cm, and the maximum taken is 80 cm because it becomes increasingly difficult to observe the stripes beyond 80 cm without the lens as the LED size is 2.06 cm. Secondly, the achievable distance is determined by using the telephoto lens based on the presence of stripes on the frames. The DTR of the communication link is determined by measuring the number of bits transmitted in

(a) Without Telephoto Lens

(b) With Telephoto Lens

Fig. 7: Two types of experiment: With and Without the telephoto lens.

a one-second video. The number of frames per second (fps) is used as a metric to quantify the number of video frames captured in one second. The video is divided into frames, and by analyzing the fps, the DTR is calculated over a specific range of distances (15-80 cm).

For the experiments, data is transmitted using OOK modulation with a frequency of 1 kHz. The smartphone camera records a video of the LED during transmission. The Open Camera app is used for recording, which aids in adjusting the exposure time and ISO value of the smartphone camera. In the experiments, the Galaxy A7 has an exposure time of $1/71429$ seconds and an ISO value of 100.

Experiments are conducted under three conditions: 1) no telephoto lens and no blooming effect, so that information can only be obtained from the size of the light source (minimum data rate (Figure 4a)); 2) no telephoto lens and blooming effect, i.e., there is an enlargement of the light source on the frame (maximum data rate (Figure 4b)); and 3) smartphone augmented with a telephoto lens. In the first condition, the DTR is at its minimum as the size of the light source is at its minimum. In the second condition, there is a maximum data rate as the light covers the maximum area on the frame. The third condition measures the DTR in the case of the lens, to compare the DTR with the minimum and maximum conditions.

In Figure 8, the DTR is compared when the telephoto lens is not used. The DTR is calculated for the blooming effect (maximum DTR) and without the blooming effect (minimum DTR). The theoretical results are provided for the minimum DTR conditions. At shorter distances, there is a larger difference in DTR due to the blooming effect.

Fig. 8: DTR comparison when the telephoto lens is not used.

Fig. 9: Usage of a telephoto lens with the smartphone.

Fig. 10: Usage of a telephoto lens with the smartphone.

In Figure 9, the DTR is compared when the telephoto lens is used. The telephoto lens has a significant impact on DTR. Figure 10 illustrates the ratio between using the lens and not using the lens. The ratio is calculated for both the minimum data rate condition (without blooming) and the maximum data rate condition (with blooming). The data rate is greatly improved for both conditions.

Furthermore, the defocus feature of the lens increases the size of the light source and enables the capture of more bands in a single frame. As depicted in Figure 11, the pair is 10.5 meters apart and using defocus mode, nine bands are acquired in a single frame. Moreover, the size of the LED without the lens, at a distance of 1 meter is 39 pixels. With the use of a telephoto lens in defocused mode, the size of the LED, at a distance of 37 meters, is approximately 36 pixels, indicating a substantial improvement in the communication link's range.

V. RELATED WORK

Previous research has explored different types of lenses for LED-to-camera communication in IoT devices. One study [17] used a bulky camera with a telephoto lens to improve the communication link, but this is not suitable for small IoT

Fig. 11: The appearance of the frame with the telephoto lens from 10.5 meters.

devices. Another study [18] proposed using a freeform lens to provide more uniform rectangular illumination, but this did not significantly increase the communication range and the cost of changing the lighting infrastructure was high. A recent study [19] used a cross-screen filter to diffuse the light, which increased the range, but the experimental verification was limited and the diffused light was less intense than the center of the light source. Another study [20] used a diffuser in front of the CMOS sensor, but the complexity (adding focus lens and the diffuser) and maximum range (short-range communication) were not fully resolved. Most of the proposed systems involve non attachable components or employ bulky cameras, which are not practical for low-power tiny IoT devices. Our proposed system uses a telephoto lens that can be easily attached to an IoT device to improve the communication link and data reception.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose the usage of the telephoto lens for LED-to-Smartphone camera communication to augment the system's range and data rate. The data rate and the range are mainly determined by the size of the LED in the camera frame in terms of the number of pixels. As the distance between the LED and the smartphone increases, the LED's size decreases in a frame, causing data loss. Even at short distances, especially small-size LEDs may not fill the camera frame, resulting in data loss. The telephoto lens, with its higher focal length, enables the smartphone user to perform an optimal zoom on the light source, minimizing data loss by increasing the region of interest. In addition to its large focal length, the defocus feature of the lens improves the communication range by increasing the size of the LED in the frame. Our study reveals an improvement in the data rates for LED-to-Smartphone camera communication at short distances (15-80 cm) and an increase in the maximum range with the use of the telephoto lens. For a 2 cm-sized LED at a 1 kHz modulation frequency, the range can be extended up to several meters, compared to less than one meter without the telephoto lens.

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